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DESIGNERS' VALUE JUDGMENT IN DESIGN MEETINGS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an empirical study, which was conducted in order to identify how designers deliver value in designing across different disciplines. Data collected during periods of observation provide insight into the characteristics and behavior of designers sharing the same working environment in three design disciplines, established in Graphic design, Architecture and Engineering. The present study reports findings on how designers' deliver value in collaborative meetings. The study is based on the mapping and analysis of instances of value judgment during the meetings for the design of an exhibition, a train interface and a robot. Results show similarities but also differences on the iteration and interdependency of the instances of value judgment across the three cases. We integrated the results by developing an inductive procedure of interaction during instances of value judgment in decision-making in design meetings.

Keywords: designers, value judgment, meetings.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main purposes of design research is to understand how designers' thinking and acting enhance the value of design processes and deliver value to design results (Eastman 2001, Akin 2001). In designing, as in any other activity, the deliberate expressions of preference are value-laden judgments derive from the need to take a stance and make a choice. As a process of thought, designing inevitably entails the designer making decisions (Akin 1995), either alone or in collaboration with other designers and stakeholders. The present research attempts to provide insight into how designers use value judgment to make decisions in design meetings.

In the following, the research literature about value and decision-making in design is reviewed. Further on the research question, the description of the research procedure and results are presented. The analyses of design meetings bring into evidence how designers' think and act during the design process with special emphasis on the cooperation with stakeholders. An inductive interaction procedure in the instances of value judgment for decision-making in design meetings is described.

VALUES AND DECISION-MAKING IN DESIGN

The topic of value in design has been discussed with increasing interest in the recent years. Research into value in design addresses several issues, such as the value of design as an activity and the value in design as a result. However, a knowledge gap can be drawn from literature. The study of value in designing from designers' point of view has been neglected. Especially empirical transdisciplinary studies are rare. On the other hand, the topic of value has been a pertinent element in research in decision-making. The process of decision is asserted to hinge upon evaluation on emergent criteria from the system of values attached to each consequential possibility and required choice. Choice is guided by value-indices, intermediate ends, which are in turn dependent on more final values (Ridley & Simon, 1938). In addition, it seems to be of importance to identify the conditions in which designers make value judgments and how do they prioritize values for decision-making in design.

RESEARCH ON VALUE IN DESIGN

Research approaches to value comprise three main dimensions, namely, economic value, human values and value systems. Values guide human behavior

through the selection of information, motivation and steer the action regulation and events as parts of a dynamic system with inherent contradictions (Bindé, 2004). A value system is regarded as an enduring organization of beliefs concerning preferable modes of conduct or end-states of existence along a continuum of relative importance (Rokeach, 1968). In design, emphasis has been placed on value from a user's perspective through user value theories and models (Boztepe, 2007), values in computer-human interaction design (Suchman, 1997; Friedman, 1996) and approaches to value in the building industry towards project management in architecture (Austin, 2005; Macmillan, 2006; Langford, 2007).

Value in designing is defined as: "The designer or design team makes choices at every point in the design process and most of these are value laden. Every decision at each "choice point" will give priority to certain values over others" (Marshall, 2008, p. 434). Few authors have tried to identify value from the designers' perspective on an empirical base. Design researchers have been contributing studies on value issues such as, affect-in-cognition (Dong, Kleinsmann & Valkenburg, 2009), ethical thinking in designing (Lloyd, 2009) a plural value framework for a shared language supporting value management (Prins, 2009). Such studies report results based on the analysis of meetings or approaches to value developed from experience. Insights from the literature on social mechanisms and patterns of discourse in value transfer in architecture meetings (Le Dantec & Yi-Luen Do, 2009) represent a meaningful study for this research that however, misses the identification of conditions and characteristics of how designers associate value to the design situation and narrative discourse. Besides, evidence of a core set of values in designers derived from an attempt to study values prioritization through experiments with architects and non-designers (Lera, 1981).

RESEARCH ON DECISION-MAKING IN DESIGN

Studies show that most of the designers' time is occupied making decisions. Therefore it is important to describe the conditions that surround and influence these decision points (Akin, 1995). Research in decision-making in design has been done in different disciplines such as engineering design

(Wallace, 1995), (Badke-Schaub & Gehrlischer, 2003), architecture (Mackinder & Marvin, 1982), and industrial design engineering (Akin, 1995; Cross, xxxxx). In addition several issues have been addressed, such as: methods and tools for decision-making (Wallace, 1995), design decisions under uncertainty (Beheshti, 1993), (Daalhuizen, Badke-Schaub & Batill, 2009) context, task and institutional environment of decision-making (Little, 1990), patterns of decision-making in design (Badke-Schaub & Gehrlischer, 2003), comparative studies on consensus and single leader decision-making (Yang, 2010), a philosophy based model for ethical decision-making in design (D'Anjou, 2010). Summarizing different reported influences on decision-making we arrive at a group of factors and processes, such as: experience, use of information from previous projects, intuition, culture, personality, predicted or unforeseen elements of risk, chain of known and unknown design constraints, unknown design variables, interaction of alternative courses of action, validity of design concepts, design intentions, and further more. Such factors of influence in decision-making in design are based on studies in a single design discipline.

This result suggests that a transdisciplinary approach to value judgment and decision-making in design based on empirical studies is necessary to overcome the sparseness of contributions.

The present study contributes to research on value in designing from designers' point of view in the context of designing in interaction with stakeholders. Such conditions can only be observed in the social context of the designing activity in the daily life environment of design offices.

This study is concerned with the question of how far, designers' instances of value judgments in different design disciplines share common and dissimilar distinct characteristics. Commonalities and differences in designing across disciplines have been asserted as of a major importance to design research in order to be able to define what is 'specific' about designing (Visser, 2009). The present study is focused on how designers prioritize value judgment and how it changes across different design domains. Thus, the research question is as follows:

How do instances of value judgment evolve in design

meetings across design disciplines?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This case study-based approach is an exploratory research approach by which we aim to identify characteristics of how designers' think and act when delivering value in design across disciplines. Data were assessed in field studies in different design environments, for the design of an exhibition in the graphic design case, the design of a train interface in the architecture case and the design of a robot in the engineering case. Sequential meetings were audio and video recorded for content analysis in Interact software*.

The study was guided by the search for instances of explicit value judgments leading to a decision, thereby paying specific attention to the following events: verbal exchanges and mechanisms of influence in the decision process. In an iterative approach the observed behavior had been coded from the videos. In the following, a description of each project provides detailed information about the

sequence of meetings per case. The presence per meeting and activity of each team member are shown (Tables 1, 2, 3).

THE DIFFERENT CASE STUDIES

In the Graphic design case study the period of observation of the design of an exhibition took six sequential weeks in which six meetings involving the customer, took place (see Table 1). The first three weeks were dedicated to the generation and development of ideas. The second meeting took place in the fourth week for task clarification. After meeting two the argumentations for discussion were flowing. In meeting three the design team and the client representatives discussed the content and structure of the exhibition. Issues such as conditional objects, set of elements to exhibit, contract details, fine-tuning costs, and budgets were discussed. In meeting four the design, construction, and client teams met at the place of the exhibition to discuss the implementation and completion of works.

Week	1 st	4 th	5 th			6 th
Meeting	1	2	3	4	5	6
Duration	2h:21 min	1h:59 min	3h:48 min	42 min	1h:27 min	1h:58 min
Topic	First concept ideas	Meeting of the client's and the design teams.	Discussion of the exhibition content	Visiting the place with construction team.	Presenting a final solution to the client.	Detailed discussion of production plan
Stage	Development of ideas	Task clarification	Analysis of requirements	Context analysis	Presenting final solution	Production planning
Team members						
Client project manager	☐	☐			☐	
Client Historicist 1		☐	☐		☐	
Client Historicist 2		☐			☐	
Client design manager	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	
Leading designer	☐	☐	☐		☐	☐
Graphic designer	☐	☐	☐		☐	☐
Designer 1 (Producer)	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Architect				☐		☐
Designer 2 (Producer)		☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Designer (scenarios)			☐	☐	☐	☐
Construction team				☐		

Table 1. Overview of meetings during the period of observation of the design of an exhibition in the Graphic design consultancy.

The meeting was focused in effective approaches to cope with undefined elements, timing and planning. In meeting five the leading designer presented the final solution concept and structure to the client's team. During this meeting several sub-solutions discussed and elaborated. In meeting six, the design team started the detail design stage, discussing and fine-tuning the materialization of sub-solutions and the production plan of the exhibition.

In the Architecture case study the period of observation of the design of a train interface took four sequential weeks in which seven meetings took place (see Table 2). In the first week three meetings were dedicated to the analysis of the context, development of ideas and task clarification together with a visit to the place of intervention. In the second week two meetings took place for a more detailed analysis of requirements and presenting two

solutions to the client. Issues such as global solution, budgets, supporting structure, and detailed design of the hedge were discussed. In the third week a

meeting to discuss detail design solutions took place. In the fourth week the design team was dedicated to plan and prepare a final presentation.

Week	1 st			2 nd		3 rd	4 th
Meeting	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Duration	1h:47 min	2h:22 min	37 min	2h:04 min	3h:32 min	1h:47 min	45 min
Topic	Context analysis, First concept ideas	After a visit to the place with construction team	Analysis of the program for a global solution	Detailed discussion of the program and solution	Presenting the solution to the client.	Detail design of several issues	Production of design output to exhibit
Stage	Context analysis	Development of ideas	Task clarification	Analysis of requirements	Presenting solution	Detailing	Preparing final presentation
Team members							
Client project manager							
Leading architect							
Architect organization							
Architect details							
Architect infrastructures							

Table 2. Overview of meetings during the period of observation of the design of a train interface in the Architecture consultancy.

In the Engineering case study eight sequential meetings took place during a period of observation of five months for the design of a robot (see Table 3). This project was settled in the academic environment, as a subject of a research project in collaboration with a design team of technical engineers with different background activities. In the first month three meetings were dedicated to the analysis of specifications, team organization production planning and task clarification. The

design was based on a previous similar robot, nevertheless the team faced several unexpected situations and challenges. In the second month a fourth meeting initiated the testing and detailing tasks that last until the end of the observation period. In the last two months the analysis of specifications, connection systems, power supply, fine-tuning costs, and identification and analysis of problems were dominant issues.

Month	1 st			2 nd	3 rd	4 th		5 th
Meeting	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Duration	1h:03 min	1h:03 min	1h:10 min	54 min	36 min	52 min	1h:01 min	42 min
Topic	Detailed discussion about the specifications and solutions	Planning, outsourcing and power supply	Discussion about the internal communication	Assembly of sub-parts, connections, testing and details	Discussion of software, defining tests and connections	Identification of problems, connections and detail	Complete assembly, Identification of problems, detailing and testing	Identification of problems, detailing and testing
Stage	Analysis of requirements	Production planning	Task clarification	Planning Testing and detailing	Analysis of requirements	Analysis of problems and Detailing	Testing, analysis of problems and detailing	Testing, analysis of problems and detailing
Team members								
Leading researcher								
Electronics Engineer								
Software Engineer								
Technician								

Table 3. Overview of meetings during the period of observation of the design of a robot in the Engineering consultancy.

In general and across the different meetings of the three design disciplines, value judgments became more frequent during the stages of analysis, more clearly expressed during the meetings with the clients to present the global solution, and based in a more detailed discussion in the detail design meetings as the designs evolved towards completion.

RESULTS

From the analysis of the meetings across the 3 design projects, the instances of value judgments occurred under the following circumstances: each time a requirement is made an instance of value judgment is settled to which an output is given - an immediate or a postponed decision. Results from the analysis of the meetings show that instances of value judgment

can be definitive or iterative. The definitive instances lead to a decision. The iterative instances do not have a definitive decision, and might be dependent on correlated instances of value judgment regarding other requirements. Requirements are made based on priority issues that are planned or emerge during the process and that can be based on conditions, restrictions or suggestions. In each one of the referred instances of value judgments priority issues initiate the discussion and settle lines of argumentation. Some requirements lead to passive situations that later on in the process become iterative. Situations of value judgment evolve towards finding the matching solution to each priority issue. Priority issues can be design related or non-design related. Definitive value judgment situations can become iterative. We developed a categorization system about the different activities during the design process. Beyond instances of value judgment, situations of reviewing, checking lists, updates, jokes relating to critical situations, delays, clarifying doubts, isolated reference and comparison to other projects occurred during the meetings. Such characteristics are common to the three design cases and became part of the analysis procedure. In the following an example of value judgment and emergence of priority issues are shown in a transcript of a sequence of an iterative and a definitive instance of value judgment.

Iterative instance of value judgment with no final decision related to the priority issue:

How to integrate the kindergarten space and which considerations need to be taken in account:

Set 4 _ 00:05:40:00 - 00:09:12:16.

“Designer A - We will do here the space for the children. (Pointing out in the drawing of the plan)

Client B - Even for another reason.

Designer A - If it was there, the parents would have to walk 400 meters (Pointing out in the drawing of the plan)

Client B - There is other unbeatable argument. We would need 70 000 Euros to have that space in conditions. It’s out of question.

Designer A - Hei, no. It’s better to spend it here. (Pointing out in the drawing of the plan)

Client B - we can do it in one of two places. It happens here, or it happens there as a multiuse space with programmed activities for the children,

and programmed activities for adults in the evenings. We can use the same materials. I will speak again with X explaining the alternatives so that she can reformulate her proposals.

Designer A - My idea is the following. In one of our Wednesday’s meetings we would meet your specialists just to tackle this part. Or you give us an A4 with what could be the program of activities for the children. Because, we don’t have to use all this area, we can just use this one, which is huge. See the scale. So, to the floor, we use the typical material you use in public children playgrounds, and a slide, those balls where they jump in, those things with ropes that they climb, tables and chairs so they can have atelier activities, and toilettes just for children, and, once there will be little ones, an area where they can take a nap. In this same area we need a compartment to have some food and drinks for the children. The program you will give to us will lead to the organization of this space. What we think is that this might be the right place. People get out of the exhibition and can walk through this way or that way, we’ll see, and end up here to collect their coats. They left their coats here in the beginning thus, we would have a wall here, marking the entrance to the children’s place. It’s completely isolated. (Pointing out in the drawing of the plan)

Client A - Can I give a suggestion? (Affirmative movements from the others) Which is to take some of this area to - from an exit point of view, some people might even arrive in group - have a lounge of arrival and departure.

Designer A - Very well. So we move the children area here and have the lounge there. This can be support area for both.” (Pointing out in the drawing of the plan)

In this transcript a discussion evolves around the issue without final decision. Partial choices and measures are made to reach a solution further on.

Definitive instance of value judgment with final decision related to the priority issue:

How to integrate a bar, esplanade and services to support such functions.

Set 5 _ 00:09:12:17 - 00:10:19:17.

“Designer A - In the same way, we have to study with you the best place for a esplanade and supporting services for a canteen.

Client B - It’s outside.

Designer A - In open air?

Client B - What was planned is to give support not just there but also outside, and to the foundation in general. (Pointing out in the drawing of the plan)

Designer A -Very well.

Client B - In the outside there is an area with a container with a lawn around it and a pine. It's a nice setting, with shadow.

Client A - On that support we can have a deck, a kiosk and some tables and chairs.

Designer A - Then, we just have to provide the caviar.”

In this transcript a discussion evolves around the issue with a final decision.

MAPPING OF THE MEETINGS

The priority issues and its related instances of value judgment were mapped for each group of meetings in excel files and coded in interact software*.

Figure 1. Mapping of the instances of value judgment during meetings for the designing of an exhibition in the Graphic design case study.

Relative frequencies are depicted (Figures 1, 2 and 3) and show the utterances of iterative and definitive priority issues. From these images it is

possible to derive differences and commonalities on the iterations and interdependencies of priority issues, across the three case studies. The incidence

of iteration per priority issue across the meetings is illustrated on the chart at the bottom of each image. In the Graphic design case study (see Figure 1), the occurrence of utterances of value judgment for 60

priority issues, scores 256 iterations. Such characteristics made the mapping look extended in height.

Figure 2. Mapping of the instances of value judgment during the meetings of the design of a train interface in the Architecture case study.

In the Architecture case study (see Figure 2) 92 priority issues have been evaluated. Due to the fact that such issues are more interdependent, 64 utterances happen from a total of 52 priority issues. An incidence of 206 iterations of value judgments

together with a high interdependency and more priority issues than the previous case made the mapping look extended in width.

Figure 3. Mapping of the instances of value judgment during the meetings for the design of a robot in the Engineering case study.

In the Engineering case study (see Figure 3) 115 priority issues were uttered, from which a total of 93 judgments were coded as iterative with 13

interdependencies. Such characteristics made the mapping look short in height and the most extended

in width. More issues had been raised but less connected, more isolated.

In the design of the robot, designers had to deal with more priority issues regarding components, sub-components, systems, mainly in order to specify characteristics. Interdependencies are related to essential elements to make the robot operational and requirements for testing and outsourcing. In the design of the train station interface, the highest amount of interdependencies is related with small changes that have repercussion in the structure of a coherent and global design solution. In the design of the exhibition, the highest amount of iterations is due to the need to find representations to each part and content of the exhibition with influence in the global design and structure. Such task demands more creativity. The above-mentioned numbers are absolute.

In the reminder of this paper we will take a closer look at the frequencies of:

- Iterations of value judgment
- Iterations of priority issues
- Interdependencies of value judgment
- Interdependencies of priority issues
 - Per case study
 - Across disciplines.

ITERATIONS OF VALUE JUDGMENT ACROSS CASE STUDIES

The iterations of value judgment across disciplines are illustrated (see Table 4). In the graphic design case, three iterative priority issues were evaluated as dominant across meetings, what makes this case the most iterative one. One reason for the more frequent iterations is due to the delays in receiving the content of the exhibition from the client provoked much iteration.

In the architecture design case, due to the high interdependency between priority issues the case shows a bit less iteration than the graphic design case. In the engineering case, although the number of priority issues is even higher (see Table 5), iterative situations are few. A detailed analysis of iterative issues across cases is further developed.

Case Study	Iterations of value judgment	Relative Numbers (%)
Graphic design	256	46,13
Architecture	206	37,12
Engineering	93	16,76

Table 4. Total and relative numbers of iterations per project regarding each design discipline.

ITERATIONS OF PRIORITY ISSUES ACROSS CASE STUDIES

Results show the frequency and most iterative priority issues per case. The incidence of priority issues per case study is illustrated (see Table 5).

Case Study	Priority Issues	Relative Numbers (%)
Exhibit design	60	22,47
Train interface	92	34,46
Robot	115	43,07

Table 5. Total and relative numbers of priority issues per project of each case study.

The relative frequency of the most iterative priority issues across the three groups of meetings per design project is exemplified (see Figure 4). In the Graphic design case, the most iterative priority issues are design related, namely: *explanation and discussion of the global solution, request and discussion of the content of the exhibition, providing awareness for the construction of the exhibition, form given to the central path of the exhibition and form given to the last path of the exhibition*. In the Architecture design case, the most iterative priority issues are design related, namely: *explanation and discussion of the global solution, modulation, supporting structure, people circulation path and space organization*. In both cases the iterative issues relate to the global design solution, structural support and construction.

In the Engineering case, the most iterative priority issues, are design and non-design related, namely: *discussion about production planning and deadlines, looking for specifications for the CPU, looking for the specifications for the battery, design of the hip board, and fine-tuning costs*.

Figure 4. Relative frequency of the most iterative priority issues per case study.

INTERDEPENDENCIES OF VALUE JUDGMENT ACROSS CASE STUDIES

The interdependencies of value judgment across disciplines are illustrated (see Table 6).

Case Study	Interdependencies of value judgment	Relative Numbers (%)
Graphic design	13	14,44
Architecture	64	71,11
Engineering	13	14,44

Table 6. Total and relative numbers of interdependencies per project regarding each design discipline.

The most frequent interdependencies between iterative instances of value judgment occurred in the Architecture case study with 64 utterances. Every single change of placement of an element would change the modulation and consequently the supporting structure and global design. One decision involved many other priority issues. In the graphic design case interdependencies relate to missing information regarding the content of the exhibition. In the engineering case study interdependencies are related to the requirements for testing and outsourcing (see Figure 5).

INTERDEPENDENCIES OF PRIORITY ISSUES PER CASE STUDY

Results based on total and relative numbers show the interdependency aspects of priority issues per case study (see Table 7).

Case Study	Interdependencies of priority issues				
	Total	Min issues	Max issues	Issues	Freq.
Exhibit design	13	2	4	11	36
Train interface	64	2	8	52	200
Robot	13	2	3	12	28

Table 7. Total numbers of interdependencies per project of each case study.

The architecture case study shows a high number of issues per interdependency situations and frequency. The other two cases have similar results.

The most interdependent priority issues are illustrated (see Figure 5). In the Graphic design case, most interdependent priority issues are design related, namely: *explanation and discussion of the global solution*, *discussion of the 1st, 2nd and 3rd paths of the exhibition* and *request and discussion of the content of the exhibition*. In the Architecture design case, the most interdependent priority issues are also design related, namely: *supporting structure*, *modulation*, *detail design*, *locating complementary functions* and *design of the facade*. In the Engineering case, the most interdependent priority issues, entail both, design and non-design related, namely: *design of the hip board*, *discussion about production planning and deadlines*, *looking for the specifications for the battery*, *request for testing*,

looking for specifications for the CPU, and request more details about the power board.

Figure 5. Relative frequency of the most interdependent priority issues instances of value judgment per case study.

ITERATIONS AND INTERDEPENDENCIES OF DESIGN AND NON-DESIGN RELATED ISSUES ACROSS CASE STUDIES

General results based on relative numbers across cases (see Figure 10) show that the number of priority issues is the lowest in the graphic design case compared to the engineering case, however the number of iterations is higher in the Graphic design case and the number of interdependencies is considerably higher in the Architecture case.

Case Study	Design related issues	Relative Numbers (%)		Non-design related issues
Exhibit design	34	12,73	9,74	26
Train interface	68	25,47	8,99	24
Robot	63	23,60	23,60	52

Table 8. Total and relative numbers of design related and non-design related issues per project regarding each design discipline.

Analyzing the priority issues per case, the Graphic design case shows a balance between design and non-design related issues. The Architecture case has the highest incidence of design related issues and more than non-design related issues. The Engineering case shows the highest incidence of non-design related issues although it has more design related issues than the Graphic design case. Although concerning with different content, some design

related common categories of priority issues are exemplified (see Figure 6).

Invariant design related priority issues
Global strategies
Guiding principles
Context
Form given
Anticipation strategies
Prevailing strategies
Locating and defining complementary functions
Conditional elements
Safety
Access
Detail

Table 9. Invariant design related priority issues.

Some non-design related common categories of priority issues are also depicted (see Table 10).

Invariant non-design related priority issues
Organization
Validation
Building
Costs
Stakeholders and outsourcing
Technical drawings
Exchange
Measuring

Table 10. Invariant non-design related priority issues.

Some specific non-design priority issues were found in the engineering case that regards *experiments*.

As an example, the priority issues related to the sub-category of *communication* under the main category of *exchange* have different meaning across the cases. In the graphic and architecture cases, communication issues relate to the way the content

of the exhibit or the design is communicated while in the Engineering case relates to the internal communication of the object, in this case the robot. General results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 10. Relative incidence of priority issues, design and non-design related issues and its iterations and interdependencies across the three case studies.

DISCUSSION OF AN INTERACTION PROCEDURE FOR VALUE JUDGMENT IN DESIGN MEETINGS

From the research findings on priority issues and analysis of instances of value judgments across the three cases an inductive description of how designers' proceed in delivering value in design meetings is illustrated. Three main elements constitute the procedure, namely, an input, an instance of value judgment and an output:

- There is an input situation based on a requirement to discuss a priority issue. Priority issues are based on a 'need', 'wish' or 'must' in the terminology of design methodology (Pahl & Beitz, 2007).
- There is an instance of value judgment that follows a pattern of procedure. From the analysis of the requirement it evolves in four alternative directions, namely: an immediate decision derived from a direct analysis; an evaluation stage where priority values emerge and guide a narrative discourse; the direct search for information or delegating activities and consequent feedback; and finally, an action-driven simulation stage that reinforces the narrative discourse of the design team. All the

possible combinations between the paths of procedure are contemplated (Figure 11).

- There is an output situation where a team-based decision is made. Two things can happen, a decision based on the agreement of a solution, or a postponed decision based on alternatives of solution. The former situation leads to iterative instances of value judgment through the meetings until reach a final decision.

The same flow diagram can be extended to the behavior of the clients and other stakeholders when delivering value in design meetings, however, with less influence in the final decisions. The narrative discourses between elements of the design team and client's team were based in the minimization of input measured as cost, and the maximization of output measured in terms of result.

CONCLUSIONS

Results show characteristics of value judgment in design meetings across the three case studies. Iterations and interdependencies of instances of value judgment and priority issues are the variables we chose to analyze the designers' practices of value delivery. These three variables show differences across the three evaluated disciplines. However,

next to the diversity of designers' value systems also commonalities can be derived from this study. The following characteristics of how designers think and act when delivering value to design meetings can be asserted:

1. Designers share categories of priority issues that initiate instances of value judgment towards decision-making (Table 9 and 10).
2. Designers share combinations of procedures in instances of value judgment towards decision-making.

A second level of analysis on the common priority issues, such as, anticipation and prevailing strategies, might bring further insights on the patterns of designers' thinking and acting according to value delivery.

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